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BUDAPEST UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND
ECONOMICS

Department Faculty of Natural Sciences
Institute of Mathematics

MASTER THESIS

Traffic Prediction Using Time Series Models

Author:
Waleed Ahmed

Supervisor:
Dr. Benczur Andras
ELKH SZTAKI

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Abstract

As urban traffic congestion continues to pose significant challenges worldwide, accurate traffic prediction models are crucial for effective traffic management and efficient transportation systems. This thesis presents a comprehensive study on traffic prediction using SKTIME models, focusing on two prominent datasets: METR-LA and PEMS-BAY.

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the effectiveness of SKTIME models in predicting traffic patterns and compare their performance across the METR-LA and PEMS-BAY datasets. To achieve this, an in-depth exploration of the datasets was performed, encompassing data preprocessing, feature engineering, and model development. The METR-LA dataset contains real-time traffic data from loop detectors in the Los Angeles area, while the PEMS-BAY dataset encompasses traffic information from various sensors in the San Francisco Bay Area.

In Chapter 2, the SKTIME time series models were thoroughly analyzed to understand their characteristics, such as motivation and methodology. Subsequently, appropriate preprocessing techniques, like imputation methods and reshaping of the datasets, were applied to the datasets to ensure data quality and consistency. Several SKTIME models were implemented of both deterministic and probabilistic nature. These models were carefully trained and tested using appropriate evaluation metrics to optimize their performance. This comparative study involves analyzing the models' accuracy, efficiency, and generalization capabilities across the METR-LA and PEMS-BAY datasets.

The findings of this research in Chapter 3 provide valuable insights into the applicability of SKTIME models for traffic prediction tasks. Through extensive experimentation and analysis, the study highlights the strengths of each model in capturing the complex dynamics of traffic patterns in the respective datasets. The results shed light on the impact of dataset characteristics on model performance. Furthermore, this thesis contributes to the field of traffic prediction by emphasizing the importance of dataset selection and preprocessing techniques in improving prediction accuracy.

In conclusion, this thesis presents a comprehensive study on traffic prediction using SKTIME models, focusing on two benchmark datasets. The research provides valuable insights into the effectiveness and applicability of SKTIME models in capturing traffic patterns, considering the unique characteristics of the datasets. The findings contribute to the field by offering practical recommendations and paving the way for further advancements in traffic prediction techniques.

List of Abbreviations

BTC	Bitcoin
OHLC	Open High Low Close
TS	Time Series
SKTIME	Scalable Kernel-based Time series classification
KNN	Kernelized Nearest Neighbor
SVM	support vector machines
STL	Seasonal and Trend Decomposition using Loess
SES	Simple Exponential Smoothing
sp	Seasonality Parameter
EWMA	Exponentially Weighted Moving Average
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
LS	Least Squares
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
MSPE	Measn Square Prediction Error
RMSPE	Root Mean Square Percentage Error
MdSPE	Median Squared Percentage Error
RMdSPE	Root Median Squared Percentage Error

Chapter 1

Introduction to Time Series

1.1 Introduction and Examples

A time series is a sequence of ordered observations x_t , which is the value of variable x at a time t . In statistical mathematics, time series can be defined as:

Definition 1.1.1 (Time Series). Let $T \neq \emptyset$ be an index set, which would be considered as time variable. A family $(X_t : t \in T)$ is a stochastic process, and a realization of (X_t) is called a time series [1].

Definition 1.1.2 (Stochastic Process). In simple words, a stochastic process is a sequence of random variables (can be discrete or continuous). It is an object with two inputs, space value and time value. For a fixed time value, it is just a random variable. And for a fixed space value, it is just a real-valued (in most real-life applications) sequence of numbers.

Types of Time Series

Discrete Time Series: When the index set T , defined above, is a countable set, the resulting time series is a discrete time series. Often for discrete time series, $T = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$.

Continuous Time Series: When the index set T , defined above, is an uncountable set, the resulting time series is a continuous time series. Often for continuous time series, $T = \mathbb{R}_+ := [0, +\infty)$.

Remark. Please note that T does not have negative numbers, as time cannot be defined for negative values.

Time series is the process of analyzing data points collected over a defined period of time, serving the purpose of identifying trends, the patterns and forecasting future values. It has been widely adapted in finance, economics, bio-medicine, and social sciences. We discuss some important examples of time series and how they are relevant.

Example 1: Stock Prices

Stock Price is perhaps the most useful example of a time series. The daily closing

FIGURE 1.1: Bitcoin price from May 2020 to March 2023.
Source: <https://www.tradingview.com/chart/?symbol=BINANCE%3ABTCUSDT>

price of a certain stock can be plotted over a certain period of time to visualize the performance of that stock for that certain period of time. It can further be analyzed for trends and patterns to look for the prices which are a level of interest.

Figure 1.1 shows the monthly levels (monthly OHLC) for the Futures contract of Bitcoin (BTC).

Example 2: Climate Data

Climate Data is also a time series data, with which we can predict the rainfall, temperature and other key variables. It not only benefits the daily social life but huge agricultural and economical decisions can be made.

Figure 1.2 shows the minimum average temperature (in blue) and maximum average temperature (in red) while the green bars show the expected precipitation for the months of 2023. This can help the people and the government make some important decisions which are influenced by climate.

Countless further examples exist in many important sectors. In economics, the analysis of patterns of GDP and GNP, forecasting of inflation, business cycles evaluation, all of these are done through methods and models of time series. In traffic prediction, which is going to be the soul of this thesis, time series helps in building the models which help predict the traffic, so that we can identify traffic anomalies, identify important routes and thus optimize traffic flow, and so on so forth. Similarly, there are countless examples from all areas of science. However to develop a sound theory, we take a statistical (rather mathematical) approach that would help us better understand: trend, seasonality, cycles, random fluctuations, etcetra.

Statistician, not just for the purpose of simplicity but for further theory building, assumes that the time series which is under consideration, can be broken down into [2]:

- deterministic trend

FIGURE 1.2: Expected Monthly Temperature and Precipitation for Budapest 2023. Source: <https://www.climatestotravel.com/climate/hungary/budapest>

- seasonal component
- a random (noise or error) component

which mathematically gives rise to the model

$$X_t = m_t + s_t + \epsilon_t \quad (t \in T) \quad (1.1)$$

where T is the time index on which time series is defined, m_t denotes the deterministic trend, s_t denotes the seasonal component, and ϵ_t is the random noise, which generally is another zero-mean stochastic process.

Chapter 2

Time Series Models in SKTIME

Time series models are statistical techniques that are used to analyze the data, identify the trends and seasonality, and forecast for future based on the historical given data. These models give insights to the unknown and true distribution of the process that generates the data.

Time series models work way differently than general machine learning models which is based on the fact that time series models give better handle time-dependent data. The basic thing that differentiates is that general machine learning model, say decision trees, work the same with any ordering of the data.

Time series models also often require a different set of assumptions and techniques compared to other machine learning models. For example, time series models often assume that the data has a specific statistical distribution, such as a normal distribution or a Poisson distribution. They may also require specific techniques for data preprocessing, such as removing trends or seasonality, or techniques for handling missing data.

Finally, time series models often require a different set of performance metrics compared to other machine learning models. For example, accuracy alone may not be an appropriate metric for evaluating a time series model since predictions that are close in time may be more important than predictions that are further in the future.

Over the last decades, the prominent programming language for statisticians was R. But in recent years, due to the shift from R to Python in the data science programming ecosystem, multiple time-series package emerged for Python. One of them is SKTIME.

2.1 Introduction to SKTIME

Over the last decades, R[3] has been the predominant programming language for statisticians. However, in recent years, there has been a notable shift within the data science programming ecosystem from R to Python. As a result, several Python packages have emerged for time series prediction, offering alternative solutions for analyzing time-dependent data. One notable package is SKTIME.

```
1 forecaster = ExponentialSmoothing(trend="additive")
2 forecaster.fit(y_train) # y_train is the training series
3 y_pred = forecaster.predict(fh=1) # single-step ahead forecasting horizon (fh)
```

FIGURE 2.1: Example of a Basic Interface for any forecaster. Source: [6]

SKTIME (Scalable Kernel-based Time series classification) is a machine learning library for time series classification tasks [4]. It is an open-source Python library built on top of scikit-learn [5] and provides a convenient and consistent API for working with time series data. The library is designed to make it easy to work with time series classification problems, and it comes with several useful features, such as:

- **Scalable Kernel Based Approaches:** such as the kernelized nearest neighbor algorithm (KNN) and support vector machines (SVMs). These methods are designed to be scalable, so they can handle large datasets with many time series.
- **Time series preprocessing:** SKTIME provides several preprocessing tools for working with time series data, such as warping and feature extraction.
- **Support for multiple time series formats:** SKTIME supports several different time series formats, such as univariate, multivariate, and multi-output time series.
- **Support for multiple evaluation metrics:** SKTIME supports several evaluation metrics for evaluating the performance of time series classifiers, such as accuracy, F1-score, and area under the ROC curve (AUC).

Overall, SKTIME is a powerful library for time series classification tasks, providing a convenient and consistent API, preprocessing tools, and scalable kernel-based approaches to work with time series data.

2.1.1 Basic Forecaster Interface

A general basic forecaster interface has been designed for all SKTIME models. These forecasters (models) have been encapsulated in classes with a common interface [6]. The advantages to this composition is: these forecasters can be interchanged at run time and then can be composed, allowing the user to write tools that work with any forecaster and thus, to create easily complex composite models, or ensembles.

The above figure (2.1) gives an example of the interface which works for all forecasters in SKTIME.

2.1.2 Easy Composition

Since the interface is common and identical, there are a number of composite forecasters which enables the users to compose and encapsulate different forecasters

FIGURE 2.2: An illustration to how reduction works. Source: [7]

```

1 regressor = RandomForestRegressor() # from scikit-learn
2 forecaster = ReducedRegressionForecaster(regressor, window_length=10, strategy="
  recursive")
3 forecaster.fit(y_train)
4 y_pred = forecaster.predict(fh=1)

```

FIGURE 2.3: An example to the reduction interface of SKTIME. Source: [6]

as per need, and utilize all of those altogether at run-time. “As is standard, composition forecasters (or meta-forecasters) are forecasters themselves, and hence share the basic interface. This allows us treat simple and composite forecasters uniformly” [6].

Reduction

It is perhaps the most useful part of creating composite models. It basically means reducing the problem A to another problem B. For example, a common practice to forecasting time series is through regression. The strategy [1, 6] is:

1. Split the training time series into fixed-length windows and stack them on top of each other.
2. This gives a matrix of lagged values in tabular format.
3. Now this tabular (cross-sectional) data is applied to any regression model.
4. To generate forecasts, a common strategy is “recursive strategy”, which takes the last window as input to the regressor to generate one-step ahead forecasts. Other strategies are “multi-step”, “direct”, “hybrid”, etc. [1].

Figure 2.2 shows an illustration of how the reduction works and is taken from [7], while Figure 2.3 shows an example of the basic interface of SKTIME reduction [6].

```

1 forecaster = TransformedTargetForecaster([
2     ("deseasonalise", Deseasonalizer(sp=12)), # monthly seasonal periodicity
3     ("forecast", NaiveForecaster(strategy="last"))
4 ])
5 forecaster.fit(y_train)
6 y_pred = forecaster.predict(fh=1)

```

FIGURE 2.4: An example to the Pipelining interface of SKTIME. Source: [6]

```

1 forecaster = ARIMA()
2 classifier = Pipeline([
3     ("extract", FittedParamExtractor(forecaster, params=["ar_params"])),
4     ("classify", RandomForestClassifier())
5 ])
6 classifier.fit(X_train, y_train) # sktime's time series classification framework
7 y_pred = classifier.predict(X_test)

```

FIGURE 2.5: An example of feature extraction with pipelining in SKTIME. Source: [6]

Pipelining

Pipelining in SKTIME, which is influenced by Pipelining in Scikit-Learn [5], is a method of composition of transformers with a final forecaster. When fitting the pipelining the data is first transformed through different transformers and then fed to a final forecaster [6]. Since the generated forecasts are also transformed, all of those transforms are used again to invert those transformations, so that forecasted data remains in its original form and should retain the same sense and taste for further analysis.

The Figure 2.4) shows the basic interface of Pipelining. Please note that the inversion of the transformation is not shown in the picture.

Ensembling

Ensembling is the method of composing several forecasters and then finally take (weighted) average of the forecasted values as the final forecast. Much like Scikit-Learn [5], it works as a meta-forecaster with several base forecasters. There can be different approaches as to what final forecast should be generated [6, 8–10].

Feature Extraction

Forecasting algorithms have been developed in such a way as to not only predict and forecast but also to be handy in extracting the features from data. The one way to do this is by applying the time series forecaster on the time series and then extract the fitted parameters, and finally using them as features for some tabular estimator [6]. Figure 2.5 shows the use of feature extraction with pipelining.

2.2 Time series models

Following models from SKTIME have been used extensively in this thesis to predict the traffic speed data.

2.2.1 Detrender and Deseasonalizer

Detrender¹ and Deseasonalizer² are two different preprocessing steps that aim to remove the trend and seasonality components from the data, respectively.

They work in a similar fashion. They both work as transformers and transform our data accordingly. Detrender removes the trend and stores in a separate component so that the remaining residuals are more stationary and can be modeled more easily. It then allows us to train our forecasters on a detrended data and predict with a better accuracy. And then the trend, from the stored component is given back to the predicted data, so that it should be compared with the test data.

Deseasonalizer works exactly in a similar manner. The only difference is that you separate the seasonality in the data and store it in a different component.

These both work according to the classical decomposition technique called STL (Seasonal and Trend Decomposition using Loess) method. SKTIME uses STL method which decomposes the original time series into three components

$$Y(t) = S(t) + T(t) + R(t),$$

where $Y(t)$ is the original time series, $S(t)$ is the decomposed seasonal component, $T(t)$ is the decomposed trend component while $R(t)$ is the residual (remaining) component.

The STL fits locally weighted regression to the time series to estimate the trend and seasonal components say:

$$T(t) = w_T(t)'X(t)$$

$$S(t) = w_S(t)'X(t),$$

where w_T is the weight regression matrix for trend component, similarly w_S for the seasonal component, $'$ is the transpose operator and $X(t)$ is the design matrix.

Finally, a new stationary series (detrended and deseasonalized) which we have called remainder $R(t) = Y(t) - S(t) - T(t)$ is produced. For details of this mathematics, refer to [11].

Next figures depict how trend and seasonal component are realized and then subtracted. Following algorithm shows the working of detrender (deseasonalizer) in SKTIME.

This is just how the detrender and deseasonalizer works, as only one can be used without the other. However, SKTIME allows us to have operability of forecasting as well. By default, Theta forecaster³ is used as the main forecaster to

¹https://sktime-backup.readthedocs.io/en/v0.13.3/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.transformations.series.detrend.Detrender.html

²https://sktime-backup.readthedocs.io/en/v0.13.3/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.transformations.series.detrend.Deseasonalizer.html

³It is explained in the next subsection

FIGURE 2.6: (Top) Original data and (bottom) realized trend component by STL. Source: [11]

FIGURE 2.7: (Top) Realized Seasonal component by STL and (bottom) remainder series after detrending and deseasonalizing. Source: [11]

Algorithm 1 Detrender (Deseasonalizer) Algorithm, source : [11]**Input:** Time series Y with trend (seasonality)**Output:** Detrended (Deseasonalized) time series Y_d

- 1: Divide the time series Y into sub-series Y_s by averaging the values of Y over each seasonal period.
- 2: For each seasonal sub-series Y_s :
 - Apply the STL algorithm to Y_s to estimate the trend component T_s and the residual component R_s .
 - Compute the seasonal component S_s by subtracting T_s and R_s from Y_s i.e. $S_s = Y_s - T_s - R_s$.
- 3: Aggregate the trend components T_s and residual components R_s across all seasonal sub-series to obtain the overall trend component T and residual component R for the entire time series Y .
- 4: Compute the deseasonalized time series Y_d by subtracting the estimated seasonal component S from Y : $Y_d(t) = Y(t) - S(t)$

predict the detrended/deseasonalized data. However, any SKTIME forecaster can be used. In fact, for our analysis purposes, we have used a bunch of different forecasters to get the best models.

The procedure is of the simplest form in SKTIME. A time series $Y(t)$ and a forecasting window, which is called “forecasting horizon” is given to the model. The model first applies the listed algorithm to get trend $T(t)$ and seasonal $S(t)$ components. Second, by subtracting these components from original series, it gets a stationary series $Y_d(t)$. This all is done by **transform()** tool. Next, it applies the forecaster on the stationary series (as the performance of forecaster would increase in case of stationary series) by using **fit()** tool. Then, using forecasting horizon, model uses **predict()** tool to calculate the forecasts. As these forecasted time series is for the stationary series $Y_d(t)$, it finally uses **inverse_transform()** tool and apply on the forecasted stationary time series. Those, already saved, trend $T(t)$ and seasonal $S(t)$ components are added back to the stationary forecasted series, and voila, we have the forecast for the original time series.

2.2.2 Theta Forecaster

Theta Forecaster is a probabilistic machine learning method to learn time series. This method is equivalent to **Simple Exponential Smoothing** [2, 12–14], referred to as SES, with drift, as explained in [15].

The Theta method is based on the idea of fitting a seasonal model to the data, and then using it to forecast future values. The method decomposes a time series into its trend, seasonality, and residual components. It does this by using a linear regression model to estimate the trend and seasonality, and the residuals are obtained by subtracting the estimated trend and seasonality from the original data.

The Theta method can be used in both univariate and multivariate time series data. The method is particularly useful for time series data that exhibit a clear

seasonal pattern, as it is able to accurately capture and forecast this pattern. The mathematics behind this forecaster is pretty detailed and can be found in [16]. However, we explain below in a much more concise manner, thanks to [15].

Let $\{X_t\}$ be the given time series. Construct another time series $\{Y_{t,\theta}\}$ such that for $t = 3, 4, \dots, n$ the following holds:

$$Y_{t,\theta}'' = \theta X_t'' \quad (2.1)$$

where X_t'' refers to the second difference of X_t . Since (2.1) is the second-order difference equation, its solution is:

$$Y_{t,\theta} = a_\theta + b_\theta(t-1) + \theta X_t \quad (2.2)$$

for $t = 1, \dots, n$ and a_θ, b_θ are constants. It is equivalent to a linear function of X_t with a linear trend added and is also called *theta line* [16]. To find the values of these constants, we minimize the sum of squared differences:

$$\sum_{i=1}^t [X_i - Y_{i,\theta}]^2 = \sum_{i=1}^t [(1-\theta)X_i - a_\theta - b_\theta(i-1)]^2 \quad (2.3)$$

with respect to these constants and thus:

$$\hat{b}_\theta = \frac{6(1-\theta)}{t^2-1} \left(\frac{2}{t} \sum_{i=1}^t iX_i - (t+1)\bar{X} \right) \quad (2.4)$$

$$\hat{a}_\theta = (1-\theta)\bar{X} - \hat{b}_\theta \frac{(t-1)}{2}. \quad (2.5)$$

This is how $Y_{t,\theta}$ is calculated. Now the theta forecaster calculates its h -step ahead forecasts using this newly generated series. The h -step ahead forecast $\hat{X}_t(h)$ for X_t is given by [15]:

$$\hat{X}_t(h) = \frac{1}{2} (\hat{Y}_{t,0}(h) + \hat{Y}_{t,2}(h)) \quad (2.6)$$

where $\hat{Y}_{t,0}(h)$ is obtained by extrapolating the equation (2.1) and $\hat{Y}_{t,2}(h)$ is calculated by applying SES on the series $Y_{t,2}$. The underlying stochastic model is explained in [15] using the state space approach.

SKTIME, however, does this a bit differently. Rather than fitting a linear trend with the same second-order difference, it fits a linear model with predictors as lagged values for the same series. The following algorithm defines the working of Theta Forecaster in SKTIME.

The parameters in this model⁴ are:

1. **detrend:** (optional) This is a boolean parameter. If true, then the detrending is done prior to fitting the forecaster.

⁴https://www.sktime.net/en/latest/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.forecasting.theta.ThetaForecaster.html

Algorithm 2 Theta Forecaster Algorithm**Input:** Time series Y and forecasting horizon h **Output:** Point forecasts F of length h and their prediction intervals.

- 1: Fit a linear regression model to Y with lagged values as predictors, using the method of least squares to estimate the regression coefficients.
- 2: Compute the seasonal index for each observation in Y by dividing it by the average value of Y for that same season.
- 3: Fit a linear regression model to the seasonal indices with lagged values as predictors, using the method of least squares to estimate the regression coefficients.
- 4: Use those regression coefficients to generate new forecasts, using:

$$F(h) = b_0 + b_1Y(h-1) + \dots + b_nY(h-n) + b_hSI(h-1) + b_sSI(h-p)$$

where b_i are regressed coefficients of lagged variables $Y(h-i)$, b_h and b_s are regressed coefficients of seasonal index SI with period p .

- 5: Compute prediction intervals $P(h)$ for each of those forecasts by:

$$P(h) = F(h) \pm z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot \sqrt{\hat{\epsilon}}$$

where $z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}$ is the $\frac{\alpha}{2}$ percentile of standard normal and $\hat{\epsilon}$ is the estimated variance of the forecast errors.

2. **deseasonalize** : (optional) This is a boolean parameter. If true, then the deseasonalization is done prior to fitting the forecaster.
3. **sp**: Seasonal Periodicity (the number of data points between seasonal observations) is taken from the train data to forecast the test data.

2.2.3 AutoETS Forecaster

The ETS models are a family of time series models with an underlying state space model consisting of a level component, a trend component (T), a seasonal component (S), and an error term (E) [2]. These forecasting models are used to analyze and forecast data that exhibits temporal patterns such as error, trend, and seasonality. These models are typically used in applications such as financial forecasting, weather forecasting, and sales forecasting.

SKTIME package contains this family as **AutoETS**⁵, which automatically detects the best model in terms of error, trend and seasonality. The main idea behind this method is called smoothing. Smoothing refers to the techniques of smoothing noise (reducing irregular variations). It tries to eliminate the components which bring short-term fluctuations in the dataset. Common smoothing techniques include **Moving Averages**, **Exponential Smoothing**, **Lowess**, etcetra. We work with the technique of **Exponential Smoothing** in this method. It is a smoothing technique that assigns exponentially decreasing weights to the past data. In this

⁵https://www.sktime.net/en/stable/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.forecasting.ets.AutoETS.html

FIGURE 2.8: An example of double exponential smoothing. Source: OrangeMatter⁶

way, the more recent observation, the higher the rate. Due to this, exponential smoothing is also called EWMA (exponentially weighted moving average).

We define the framework for this model here:

First, exponential smoothing is based on the Holt-Winters method[17], which is further based on triple components, the level L_t , the trend T_t and the seasonality S_t . An example of double layering (without seasonality) is seen in Figure 2.8. Holt-Winters applies the following equations [18]:

$$L_t = \alpha \frac{y_t}{S_{t-K}} + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + T_{t-1}) \quad (2.7)$$

$$T_t = \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1} \quad (2.8)$$

$$S_t = \gamma \frac{y_t}{L_t} + (1 - \gamma)S_{(t-K)} \quad (2.9)$$

And then the h -step ahead forecast is given by:

$$\hat{y}_{t+h} = (L_t + hT_t) \times S_{t-K+h} \quad (2.10)$$

where y_t is the value of time series at time t , K is the seasonality period of the time series and (α, β, γ) are the respective smoothing parameters. In recent times, there have been extensions to these models where the newer versions can account for not only one seasonality

⁶<https://orangematter.solarwinds.com/2019/12/15/holt-winters-forecasting-simplified/>

The model is initialized to calculate the best values for these smoothing parameters. They can be initialized manually or calculated by the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) methods. Once those are calculated, the algorithm starts fitting the model using the above equations. The best model is chosen through optimization techniques. And finally, the future forecasts are calculated by equation (2.10).

The parameters in this model are:

1. **error:** (optional) The error model. Takes either “add” or “mul”.
2. **trend:** (optional) The trend component. Takes either “add”, “mul” or none.
3. **seasonal:** The seasonality component. Takes either “add”, “mul” or none
4. **sp:** Seasonal Periodicity (the number of data points between seasonal observations) is taken from the train data to forecast the test data. Default = 1.

2.2.4 ARIMA Forecaster

ARIMA, which stands for **Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average** [2, 19], is a commonly used time series forecasting model. It can be used to model and predict future values based on past data [20].

ARIMA models are a superset of classical Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) models. ARIMA is an amalgamation of concepts like autoregression (AR), integration (I), and moving averages (MA). These models are very useful in the case of non-stationarity. However, SKTIME arms you with preprocessing utilities like detrending and deseasonalization, for maximum accuracy. ARIMA model is developed on the extension of ARMA models in order to tackle the issue of stationarity. ARIMA introduces the concept of integration, or in simpler terms *differencing*, which essentially means to transform the data, with the help of past values, in order to achieve more accurate models. ARIMA has three primary elements:

1. **Autoregression (AR):** This component simulates the relationship of the target variable to its past values (which we call lagged data) and computes the effect of that lagged data on the current value.
2. **Integration (I):** This is the process of differencing, which essentially means transforming data by removing the trend and seasonality components in order to achieve the stationarity for the model. Usually, it is done by differencing the last value from the current one, or maybe of higher order differencing.
3. **Moving Averages (MA):** This component models the relationship between an observation and the residual errors from a moving average model applied to lagged observations, capturing the short-term dependencies in the data.

Mathematics behind ARIMA:

We give the mathematical foundations of the ARIMA model for each of the three elements.

1) AR(p) element: As it captures the dependency of current values on the past values, we have the p -past values:

$$Y_t = c + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \cdots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t. \quad (2.11)$$

2) I(d) element: As it deals with differencing the time series, we have the d -differenced values, with $\nabla^d[\cdot] = [\cdot]_t - [\cdot]_{t-1} - \cdots - [\cdot]_{t-d}$:

$$D_t = \nabla^d Y_t. \quad (2.12)$$

3) MA(q) element: As it captures the short-term dependencies, or the past q fluctuations:

$$Y_t = \mu + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} + \cdots + \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} + \epsilon_t. \quad (2.13)$$

Finally, the comprehensive and synthetic model of ARIMA has the definition:

$$\nabla^d Y_t = C + \phi_1 \nabla^d Y_{t-1} + \cdots + \phi_p \nabla^d Y_{t-p} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \cdots + \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} + \epsilon_t. \quad (2.14)$$

The parameter values can be manually given or can be calculated using some maximum likelihood methods. Once these parameters are known, the above equations are very easy to calculate. The following algorithm shows how ARIMA is carried out in SKTIME.

Algorithm 3 ARIMA Forecaster Algorithm

Input: Time series Y_t , the parameters p, q, d and forecasting horizon h .

Output: ARIMA forecasts $\hat{Y}_{t+h}$ of length h .

- 1: **Integration:** If $d > 0$, then apply the d -order differencing and remove any trend/seasonality from the differenced series to make it a stationary time series.
- 2: **Model Initialization:** Initialize the ARIMA model of order (p, d, q) on the differenced series using the above equation (2.14).
- 3: **Estimation:** To approximate the coefficients of AR and MA terms, use techniques like MLE, LS etc. Iterate over multiple combinations to find the best model based on AIC, BIC etc.
- 4: **Fitting:** Fit the ARIMA model with estimated coefficients to the preprocessed series.
- 5: **Forecasting:** Use the same equation (2.14) with all realized coefficients, and then invert the differencing to get back the original form of the time series.

The class takes several parameters to specify the model's configuration, such as the order of differencing (d), the order of the autoregressive component (p), and

the order of the moving average component (q). These parameters can be set manually, or they can be estimated using a grid search or other techniques.

The parameters in this model⁷ are:

1. **order:** The (p,d,q) order of the model for the number of AR parameters, differences, and MA parameters to use. Default is an AR(1) model: $(1,0,0)$.
2. **seasonal order:** This parameter takes input (p,d,q,s) where p,d , and q are described as above. The s component is the periodicity (number of periods in season). Often it is 4 for quarterly data or 12 for monthly data. Default is no seasonal effect $(0,0,0,0)$.

2.3 Error Metrics

To compare the forecasted values with that of the test data, we need some metrics to judge the performance of the models. To know which model works the best, we see which model performs the best in terms of yielding the least error. For this project, the following error metrics have been taken to compare the model performance.

2.3.1 Geometric Mean Absolute Error:

From SKTIME, **Geometric Mean Absolute Error (GMAE)** [12] has been taken. GMAE⁸ output is non-negative floating point. The best value is approximately zero, rather than zero.

Like MAE, GMAE is measured in the same units as the input data. Because GMAE takes the absolute value of the forecast error rather than squaring it, GMAE penalizes large errors to a lesser degree than squared error variants like MSE or RMSE.

The formula is:

$$GMAE(Y, \hat{Y}) = (\prod_{i=1}^n |Y_i, \hat{Y}_i|)^{1/n}$$

2.3.2 Mean Squared Scaled Error:

From SKTIME, **Mean Squared Scaled Error (MSSE)** [12] has been taken. MSSE⁹ output is a non-negative floating point. The best value is zero.

⁷https://www.sktime.net/en/stable/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.forecasting.arma.ARIMA.html

⁸https://www.sktime.net/en/stable/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.performance_metrics.forecasting.geometric_mean_absolute_error.html

⁹https://www.sktime.net/en/stable/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.performance_metrics.forecasting.MeanSquaredScaledError.html

This metric is also suited for intermittent-demand series because it will not give infinite or undefined values unless the training data is a flat time series. In this case, the function returns a large value instead of infinity.

In our project, we take the square root parameter to be true, hence the formula is:

$$MSSE(Y, \hat{Y}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{n} \right).$$

2.3.3 Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error:

From SKTIME, **Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE)** [12] has been taken. SMAPE¹⁰ output is a non-negative floating point. The best value is zero.

SMAPE is measured in percentage error relative to the test data. Because it takes the absolute value rather than square the percentage forecast error, it penalizes large errors less than MSPE, RMSPE, MdSPE, or RMdSPE. The formula is:

$$SMAPE(Y, \hat{Y}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2 * |y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{n * (|y_i| + |\hat{y}_i|) / 2}.$$

¹⁰https://www.sktime.net/en/latest/api_reference/auto_generated/sktime.performance_metrics.forecasting.MeanAbsolutePercentageError.html

Chapter 3

Traffic prediction

3.1 Related work

Traffic congestion has been a growing issue in almost all urban areas, the case is worst for big metropolitan cities. According to Forbes, an average person spent 99 hours in traffic per year¹. Therefore, in recent years, Traffic prediction has emerged as a critical tool for modern-day policymakers and management departments. It is incumbent in today's world for many reasons.

- **Better transport planning:** City planners have a better idea about the routes, their capacities, and the needs of people, and hence the transport is optimized for the needs of people.
- **Effective resource management:** Traffic forecasting helps managers allocate resources wisely. Transportation authorities can reduce congestion and make the most of their current infrastructure by properly forecasting traffic flows and then optimizing the allocation of traffic signal timings, adjusting toll prices dynamically, and deploying traffic management employees.
- **Better traveler experience:** Reliable traffic forecasts enable commuters to plan their routes and journey times with greater knowledge. Travelers can select other routes, modes of transportation, or departure times thanks to real-time traffic information and prediction algorithms, which eventually cuts down on their overall travel time and annoyance.
- **Emergency response planning:** By predicting traffic patterns during catastrophes or disasters, traffic prediction assists emergency response planning. By using this data, authorities may plan effective evacuation routes, deploy resources wisely, and update the public in real-time, resulting in quick and effective disaster response.

By definition, traffic data prediction is the process of using statistical models and machine learning techniques to analyze historical traffic data and predict future

¹<https://www.forbes.com/sites/jimgorzelany/2023/01/10/these-are-the-us-cities-where-motorists-lose-the-most-time-and-money-sitting-in-traffic/>

traffic patterns. This can be used for a variety of purposes, such as traffic management, transportation planning, and incident response.

A common way to tackle this problem is time series prediction. In my work, I use time series models from the SKTIME Python package². These models can analyze and predict patterns in data over time. Another popular technique to solve traffic prediction-related problems is recursive neural networks, such as long short-term memory (LSTM) networks, which are particularly well-suited for predicting time series data and can take into account both past and future values.

Another important aspect of traffic data prediction is the multiple sources of data, such as traffic surveillance cameras, traffic sensors, GPS enabled devices etc. This makes the whole traffic prediction very handy with a ready to use real-time data.

Overall, traffic data prediction is a valuable tool for managing and improving transportation systems, and will likely become increasingly important as cities continue to grow and urban traffic becomes more complex.

3.2 Dataset

In this thesis, I used two benchmark datasets, METR-LA and PEMS-BAY, with complex structures to conduct my experiments. The advantage of having multiple datasets is that you see whether the results of advanced and complex models generalize across different datasets. The only disadvantage of using different datasets is that you might not have the ultimate best model over all datasets. This is due to the reason that each dataset has different structure and different peculiarities, which not every model is suited to recognize. Thus, you have, say, model A working best for dataset X and model B working best for dataset Y.

3.2.1 First Dataset: METR-LA Dataset

This dataset was collected on the highway of Los Angeles County in real-time by loop detectors. **METR-LA** traffic data is widely used in traffic prediction³. The authors used 207 sensors to detect the speeds, and the dataset contains four months of data ranging from March 1st, 2012, to June 30th, 2012.

To get better insights into data, we have randomly selected ten sensors. For each sensor, the data are speeds that the sensor has detected every five minutes, and it has been aggregated into 5-minute intervals. So for each day, we have 288 entries (24*12). Finally, we average all the errors for each sensor with equal weights.

The average speed as the function of the time is shown in Figure 3.1. There is no particular distribution of this data. However, we can say that we see many spikes and outliers, with the regular speed range between 60 and 70.

²<https://www.sktime.net/en/latest/>

³<https://paperswithcode.com/sota/traffic-prediction-on-metr-la>

FIGURE 3.1: Traffic Speeds Dataset for METR-LA

3.2.2 Second Dataset: PEMS-BAY Dataset

This dataset was collected by the California Transportation Agencies Performance Measurement System (PEMS) of California County in real-time by loop detectors. **PEMS-BAY** traffic data is also widely used in traffic prediction⁴. The authors used 325 sensors to detect the speeds, and the dataset contains 6 months of data ranging from January 1st, 2017 to May 31th, 2017.

To get better insights into data, we have randomly selected 10 sensors. For each sensor, the data are speeds that sensor has detected every five minutes, and it has been aggregated into 5-minute intervals. So for each day, we have 288 entries (24*12). Finally, we average all the errors for each sensor with equal weights.

FIGURE 3.2: Traffic Speeds Dataset for PEMS-BAY

The average speed as the function of the time is shown in Figure 3.2]. There is no particular distribution of this data. However, we can see that this dataset has different minimum and maximum. The outliers are very much limited as compared to the METR-LA. Most of the data is centered around its mean.

A few words about datasets: As it was stated, there is no particular specific distribution. The spikes are actually meaningful. These may indicate holidays, road-blocks, traffic jams, and of course, the absence of people at night times. There is

⁴<https://paperswithcode.com/sota/traffic-prediction-on-pems-bay>

a (continuous) subset of data that is all just zeros, which is interpreted as a road-block due to some construction.

3.3 Experiments

3.3.1 Preprocessing Datasets

Preprocessing datasets is a crucial process before directly fitting models on the datasets. The data might have outliers, as in our case, noisy errors or missing values, which need to be imputed. Sometimes, variables on different scales need to be normalized before model training. Please note that if the fitting models are non-parametric, there is no need to check for normalization, as in our case. There can be variables that are correlated. Due to the above reasons and many others, preprocessing helps us to give better-quality data for model training.

We start by looking at the dataset. We generate the training and testing datasets according to the author's instructions [21]. However, we see that the loaded training (and similarly testing) data is four-dimensional. To use our listed models in SKTIME, we convert it to one-dimensional (time series) data with the help of `reshape`⁵ function from numpy. We do this reshaping in order to limit the data to one window. Please note that Figures 3.1 and 3.2 are after reshaping.

Also, as stated earlier, we note that there are some days (at some times) where the data of speeds is just zero. What that implies, is there was no recorded speed in that time interval. That is why we replaced those zero-valued entries with the last recorded value. Having said that, we do not either want to change the structure of data, so we perform missing value (or zero value) imputation by using the last recorded value instead of zeros. The following image shows both of the datasets (only the training part). As can be seen in Figure 3.3, the structure of the data is still the same. Only outliers have been somewhat excluded.

Now that we are ready with the data, we apply SKTIME time series models.

3.3.2 Theta Forecaster

We apply the Theta Forecaster model with no *sp* (seasonality) parameter. Since we have zero values and our datasets have multiplicative seasonality, it cannot be decomposed in that case. Also, we did not detrend or deseasonalize it due to the fact that we are using it as another complete model with more detailed parameters.

Without missing value imputation

First, we apply this forecaster to data without any missing value imputation. This is due to the fact that we need both outputs, one for imputation and one without. The results are shown in Figures 3.4 and 3.5. The errors are listed in Table 3.1.

⁵<https://numpy.org/doc/stable/reference/generated/numpy.reshape.html>

FIGURE 3.3: Before and after zero imputation for METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.4: Theta Forecaster on METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.5: Theta Forecaster on PEMS-BAY Dataset

It can be seen in Table 3.1 that the SMAPE error metric for PEMS-BAY data is relatively better, telling us that it our model works better for this dataset.

With missing value imputation

Next, we apply this forecaster on the dataset not containing zeros. Here, we set sp (seasonality) parameter to be $12 \times 24 \times 7 = 2016$ to take care of weekly seasonality. We predict better performance and better results. The results are shown in Figures 3.6 and 3.7. The errors are listed below in Table 3.2.

FIGURE 3.6: Theta Forecaster with zero imputation on METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.7: Theta Forecaster with zero imputation on PEMS-BAY Dataset

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.43715	SMAPE	0.28152
RMSSE	3.37971	RMSSE	4.70721
GMAE	4.28466	GMAE	1.96555

TABLE 3.1: Errors for Theta Forecaster Model

It can be seen that the errors have reduced significantly for METR-LA dataset. However, there is little to no difference for PEMS-BAY dataset. This is due to fact that there are very less zeros in the PEMS-BAY dataset and zero imputation for that has not helped much.

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.25311	SMAPE	0.28009
RMSSE	2.99373	RMSSE	4.79241
GMAE	2.68040	GMAE	1.96517

TABLE 3.2: Errors for Theta Forecaster Model with Zero Imputation

3.3.3 Detrender Model with Theta Forecaster

As we mentioned SKTIME has detrending models where the trend is separated from the data before applying the forecaster. We use theta forecaster as base forecaster for forecasting. In practice, we apply the detrender transform on the time series, fit the forecaster on the transformed series and forecast for the the next h-steps, finally we invert again the transformed series back to its original form, so that it can be compared to the test data.

Without missing value imputation

First we apply this model on the datasets containing zeros. The results are shown in Figures 3.8 and 3.9. The errors are listed below in Table 3.3.

FIGURE 3.8: Detrended Theta Forecaster on METR-LA Dataset

It can be seen in Table 3.3 that the errors are negligibly better. PEMS-BAY has still almost the same errors.

With missing value imputation

Next, we apply this forecaster on the dataset not containing zeros. We predict better performance and better results. The results are shown in Figures 3.10 and 3.11. The errors are listed below in Table 3.4.

It can be seen that errors are merely decreasing (or increasing in some cases). PEMS-BAY data has better errors but this betterment is negligible.

FIGURE 3.9: Detrended Theta Forecaster on PEMS-BAY Dataset

FIGURE 3.10: Detrended Theta Forecaster with zero imputation on METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.11: Detrended Theta Forecaster with zero imputation on PEMS-BAY Dataset

3.3.4 ARIMA Forecaster

We apply the ARIMA Forecaster model with no specific (p,d,q) parameter. So the default is AR(1) model.

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.43152	SMAPE	0.28107
RMSSE	3.38713	RMSSE	4.70301
GMAE	3.68056	GMAE	1.88110

TABLE 3.3: Errors for Detrended Theta Forecaster Model

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.25022	SMAPE	0.27963
RMSSE	2.99279	RMSSE	4.78817
GMAE	2.5356	GMAE	1.87720

TABLE 3.4: Errors for Detrended Theta Forecaster Model with Zero Imputation

Without missing value imputation

First we apply this model on the datasets containing zeros. The results are shown in Figures 3.12 and 3.13. The errors are listed below in Table 3.5.

FIGURE 3.12: ARIMA Forecaster on METR-LA Dataset

It can be seen in Table 3.5 that the errors are negligibly better compared to the models with the base Theta Forecaster.

With missing value imputation

Next, we apply this forecaster on the dataset not containing zeros. We predict better performance and better results. The results are shown in Figures 3.14 and 3.15. The errors are listed below in Table 3.6.

FIGURE 3.13: ARIMA Forecaster on PEMS-BAY Dataset

FIGURE 3.14: ARIMA Forecaster with zero imputation on METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.15: ARIMA Forecaster with zero imputation on PEMS-BAY Dataset

3.3.5 AutoETS Forecaster

We apply the AutoETS Forecaster model with the auto parameter to be true so that the best model is used for forecasting.

Without missing value imputation

First we apply this model on the datasets containing zeros. The results are shown in Figures 3.16 and 3.17. The errors are listed below in Table 3.7.

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.42536	SMAPE	0.27602
RMSSE	3.37618	RMSSE	4.61389
GMAE	3.74637	GMAE	1.91512

TABLE 3.5: Errors for ARIMA Forecaster Model

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.24235	SMAPE	0.27469
RMSSE	2.93773	RMSSE	4.69913
GMAE	2.55192	GMAE	1.91417

TABLE 3.6: Errors for ARIMA Forecaster Model with Zero Imputation

FIGURE 3.16: AutoETS Forecaster on METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.17: AutoETS Forecaster on PEMS-BAY Dataset

It can be seen in Table 3.7 that the errors are negligibly better. PEMS-BAY has still almost the same errors.

With missing value imputation

Next, we apply this forecaster on the dataset not containing zeros. We predict better performance and better results. The results are shown in Figures 3.18 and 3.19. The errors are listed below in Table 3.8.

FIGURE 3.18: AutoETS Forecaster with zero imputation on METR-LA Dataset

FIGURE 3.19: AutoETS Forecaster with zero imputation on PEMS-BAY Dataset

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.42747	SMAPE	0.27585
RMSSE	3.35753	RMSSE	4.63147
GMAE	3.71334	GMAE	1.88884

TABLE 3.7: Errors for AutoETS Forecaster Model

It can be seen that errors are slightly decreasing (or increasing in some cases). PEMS-BAY data still behaves the same way.

METR-LA		PEMS-BAY	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
SMAPE	0.24779	SMAPE	0.27191
RMSSE	2.97129	RMSSE	4.70275
GMAE	2.55160	GMAE	1.86699

TABLE 3.8: Errors for AutoETS Forecaster Model with Zero Imputation

3.3.6 Results

PEMS-BAY Data

Let us first talk about the PEMS-BAY dataset. All the models, be it probabilistic like Theta Forecaster or deterministic like ARIMA, worked almost similarly and produced almost the same results. This can be seen in Figure 3.20. The reason for this peculiarity is that though we have so much data, the dataset remains very, very close to its mean. The interpretation of this might be that the location from where this data is collected is a location with almost consistent traffic speed most of the time. Unlike highways, as in the METR-LA case, the speeds do not vary much. We compare the daily mean (since the data is every 5-minute instance, we average out for the whole day) of both datasets, and we can clearly see, why all the models perform similarly for PEMS-BAY but differently for the METR-LA dataset. This comparison is done in Figure 3.22. It is evident that there is way more variance in METR-LA Dataset as compared to the PEMS-BAY dataset. Due to the almost similar performance of all models, none of the error metrics, therefore, can give the best model.

FIGURE 3.20: Different Error Metrics for all listed models on PEMS-BAY data.

METR-LA Dataset

As can be seen from the Figure 3.22, the METR-LA Dataset is more robust and has more complex and unique structure, causing each model to perform differently. The best thing about this is that we can now talk about the best model as can be

FIGURE 3.21: Different Error Metrics for all listed models on METR-LA data.

FIGURE 3.22: Comparison of Daily Mean for both datasets for the first 100 days.

interpreted from Figure 3.21. Each error metric has given a best model, Table 3.9. It can be seen that ARIMA has outperformed every model in case of imputation. However, there are 3 best candidates in case of no imputation (Tables 3.10–3.11), but looking at their graphs and errors, they have performed almost similarly.

Remark. The different error metrics drawn on the same axis can be misleading and should be avoided for better clarity. However, since those error values are given in their respective tables for their respective models, we avail this luxury and plot them in the same axis.

Without Imputation		With Imputation	
Metric	Best Model	Metric	Best Model
SMAPE	ARIMA	SMAPE	ARIMA
RMSSE	AutoETS	RMSSE	ARIMA
GMAE	DET: THETA	GMAE	THETA

TABLE 3.9: Best Model for each Error Metric for METR-LA Data

FIGURE 3.23: SMAPE Error Metric for all datasets of METR-LA.

FIGURE 3.24: RMSSE Error Metric for all datasets of METR-LA.

3.3.7 Comprehensive Analysis on METR-LA Dataset

Since it is established that the PEMS-BAY dataset has not more to be explored, we dive into the METR-LA Dataset. This time series has an average value of 57.06333 due to its so many outliers. From this dataset, we generate new datasets. As stated, this data has a time difference of 5 minutes, i.e. each instance is 5 minute value of the sensor, we aggregate this, average it out, for three datasets.

- **Hourly:** We average out each 12 entries, as 5×12 makes an hour.
- **Daily:** We average out each 12×24 entries, as that makes a day.
- **Weekly:** We average out each $12 \times 24 \times 7$ entries, as that makes a week.

We perform all the listed models on these three datasets again to get a better perspective. Following figures show the results.

SMAPE

SMAPE clearly shows that overall models have performed the worst in the hourly dataset and that overall models have performed better in the daily dataset, although you have lower errors in weekly dataset but since it is not that robust,

FIGURE 3.25: GMAE Error Metric for all datasets of METR-LA.

that performance is not significant. The best models are still ARIMA and AutoETS forecasters.

RMSSE

RMSSE clearly shows that overall models have performed the worst in the hourly dataset, in accordance with SMAPE metric. The rest errors for remaining datasets are similar, and therefore, are of no interest.

GMAE

GMAE is in not so agreement with its colleague metrics, as there are models performing worse than models fitted on hourly dataset. However, it shows that the best model still remain the same for this metric, as of SMAPE.

Best Performers			
Dataset	SMAPE	RMSSE	GAME
5-minute	ARIMA	ARIMA	ARIMA
Hourly	AutoETS	AutoETS	AutoETS
Daily	ARIMA	ARIMA	ARIMA
Weekly	AutoETS	AutoETS	AutoETS

TABLE 3.10: Best Model for each Error Metric for METR-LA Data without imputation

Best Performers			
Dataset	SMAPE	RMSSE	GAME
5-minute	ARIMA	ARIMA	ARIMA
Hourly	ARIMA	ARIMA	ARIMA
Daily	THETA	ARIMA	ARIMA
Weekly	AutoETS	AutoETS	AutoETS

TABLE 3.11: Best Model for each Error Metric for METR-LA Data with zero imputation

Summary

Traffic prediction is an essential tool in the modern world. It does not only help in logistics but also determines how a city, state, or country has to act in terms of traffic management, and transport systems. Statistical techniques to predict traffic data have been very handy.

SKTIME, a library recently developed, has helped in understanding and explaining the time series in a simpler and in-depth perspective. We start by exploring the SKTIME library. We explore the approaches SKTIME facilitates the user for various purposes. We describe the SKTIME basic interface, the composition, the reduction techniques, the pipelining techniques and the feature extraction techniques.

We explore SKTIME models suited for our datasets and for the scope of this thesis. Probabilistic models like Theta Forecaster and Detrended Theta Forecaster help us in decomposing the seasonality and trends in the dataset. Deterministic models like ARIMA and AutoETS forecaster help us understand the trends and the correlation of the current values with the past values.

We take the prominent datasets of METR-LA and PEMS-BAY to predict the traffic speeds for the future time. We also made another dataset where some outliers were replaced with the last recorded values for better model performance. We applied a series of SKTIME models and analyzed their performances.

We see that almost all models performed better when we imputed missing values with the last recorded value in the case of METR-LA. However, PEMS-BAY dataset had a different story to tell. Time series models on PEMS-BAY dataset, due to its mainly being close to the mean, performed almost equally well. The zero-imputation could not give us better results as there were very few outliers (zero values). Due to this very fact, no error metric for any model was significantly less than can be reported. Hence, we fail to give the best model in this case.

The case for METR-LA dataset is quite different. Due to it being a very robust model, the imputation gave us an increased accuracy. Without the imputation, we have a different best model with the accuracy of 58.5% (for ARIMA), but when we impute the zero (missing) values, then almost all error metrics suggest the **ARIMA is the best model** with an accuracy of around 76.5% (in other words SMAPE error metric has a measure of around 0.245).

Since, the robustness of METR-LA data, we aggregate the original data (5-minute

entries) and average out to get the hourly values, daily values, and weekly values. We do so due to the fact that we wanted to capture more trends that happen in hours (day-time vs night-time), in days (weekdays vs weekends), and in weeks (like holiday vs non-holiday). We applied the same SKTIME models on these newly generated datasets and found that, with imputation, ARIMA is the best forecaster (for all error metrics) for all time windows, except for the weekly dataset.

Bibliography

- [1] Gianluca Bontempi, Souhaib Ben Taieb, and Yann-Aël Le Borgne. “Machine Learning Strategies for Time Series Forecasting”. In: vol. 138. Jan. 2013. ISBN: 978-3-642-36317-7. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-36318-4_3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-36318-4_3).
- [2] Rob Hyndman and G. Athanasopoulos. *Forecasting: Principles and Practice*. 3rd ed. OTexts, 2021.
- [3] Rob J Hyndman and Yeasmin Khandakar. “Automatic time series forecasting: the forecast package for R”. In: *Journal of statistical software* 27 (2008), pp. 1–22.
- [4] Markus Löning et al. “Sktime: A Unified Interface for Machine Learning with Time Series”. In: (2019). arXiv: [1909.07872](https://arxiv.org/abs/1909.07872) [cs.LG].
- [5] F. Pedregosa et al. “Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12 (2011), pp. 2825–2830.
- [6] Markus Löning and Franz Király. *Forecasting with sktime: Designing sktime’s New Forecasting API and Applying It to Replicate and Extend the M4 Study*. 2020. arXiv: [2005.08067](https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.08067) [cs.LG].
- [7] Joanna Lenczuk (Towards Data Science). “Why start using sktime for forecasting?” In: (2021). URL: <https://towardsdatascience.com/why-start-using-sktime-for-forecasting-8d6881c0a518>.
- [8] Felix Chan and Laurent L. Pauwels. “Some theoretical results on forecast combinations”. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 34.1 (2018), pp. 64–74. ISSN: 0169-2070. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2017.08.005>.
- [9] Jeremy Smith and Kenneth F. Wallis. “A Simple Explanation of the Forecast Combination Puzzle”. In: *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* 71.3 (2009), pp. 331–355. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0084.2008.00541.x>.
- [10] Allan Timmermann. “Chapter 4 Forecast Combinations”. In: ed. by G. Elliott, C.W.J. Granger, and A. Timmermann. Vol. 1. *Handbook of Economic Forecasting*. Elsevier, 2006, pp. 135–196. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0706\(05\)01004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0706(05)01004-9).
- [11] Robert B Cleveland et al. “STL: A seasonal-trend decomposition”. In: *J. Off. Stat* 6.1 (1990), pp. 3–73.
- [12] Rob J. Hyndman and Anne B. Koehler. “Another look at measures of forecast accuracy”. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 22.4 (2006), pp. 679–688. ISSN: 0169-2070. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2006.03.001>.
- [13] Everette S Gardner Jr. “Exponential smoothing: The state of the art”. In: *Journal of forecasting* 4.1 (1985), pp. 1–28.

- [14] Everette S. Gardner. “Exponential smoothing: The state of the art—Part II”. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 22.4 (2006), pp. 637–666. ISSN: 0169-2070. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2006.03.005>.
- [15] Baki Billah Rob J. Hyndman. “Unmasking the Theta method”. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 19.2 (2003), Pages 287–290. ISSN: 0169-2070. URL: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2070\(01\)00143-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2070(01)00143-1).
- [16] V. Assimakopoulos and K. Nikolopoulos. “The theta model: a decomposition approach to forecasting”. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 16.4 (2000). The M3- Competition, pp. 521–530. ISSN: 0169-2070. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2070\(00\)00066-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2070(00)00066-2).
- [17] Charles C. Holt. “Forecasting seasonals and trends by exponentially weighted moving averages”. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 20.1 (2004), pp. 5–10. ISSN: 0169-2070. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2003.09.015>.
- [18] Spyros Makridakis, Steven Wheelwright, and Rob J Hyndman. *Forecasting: Methods and Applications, 3rd Ed.* English. John Wiley & Sons, 1997. ISBN: 0-471-53233-9.
- [19] George EP Box. “GM Jenkins Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control”. In: *San Francisco, Holdan-Day* (1970).
- [20] James Taylor. “Short-term electricity demand forecasting using double seasonal exponential smoothing”. In: *Journal of Operational Research Society* 54 (Aug. 2003), pp. 799–805. DOI: [10.1057/palgrave.jors.2601589](https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jors.2601589).
- [21] Yaguang Li et al. “Diffusion Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network: Data-Driven Traffic Forecasting”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR '18)*. 2018.

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